

10:00 - 11:30	Session 7: Dust & Star-Formation in Galaxies	Chair: Vivian U (UCI)
10:00 - 10:30	7a Invited Talk: Daniela Calzetti (UMass, Amherst)	Dust and Star Formation in Galaxies: Not the Entire Story
10:30 - 10:45	7b Andrew Battisti (ANU)	Sweeping Away the Dust: Understanding the Evolution of Attenuation up to the Peak of Cosmic Star Formation
10:45 - 11:00	7c Claude-Andre Faucher-Giguere (Northwestern)	A new paradigm for the formation of disk galaxies & its implications for star formation variability, galactic winds, & quenching
11:00 - 11:15	7d Hermine Landt (Durham Univ)	Astrochemistry of the Dust Around Supermassive Black Holes in the New Era of Transient Infrared Sky Surveys
11:15 - 11:30	7e Anahita Alavi (IPAC)	Dust attenuation measurement for high-redshift dwarf galaxies

Session 7 live captioning on Thursday, 8 October 2020

It's 10:00 a.m. Eastern time. Welcome back, everybody. I'm **Max Mutchler**, one of the local organizers of the conference. In a minute I will turn it over to our session chair but I have brief announcements.

I would like to remind you of our Code of Conduct which is available in the slack channel. We expect everyone to abide by it. Questions and answers for each of our talks this morning will also be on slack, so please type your questions there and our session chair will ask them.

We are going to be sending out a survey to all of you later today or early tomorrow. We hope to get your feedback on how this conference is going for you. We are experimenting with a lot of new technologies and streaming these talks to Facebook and learning about how to run a virtual conference. Your feedback will be very helpful. We want to send it out early. The survey will remain open for a week or two. You can respond later as well. With that I will turn it over to our session chair, Vivian U.

Thank you. Hi, welcome to session seven which is on a star formation and galaxies. I am **Vivian U** from UC Irvine. We have one invited talk and for contributed talks. I would like to remind the speakers that I'll be giving you a five minute warning on the 20 minute talk and a two-minute warning on the 12 minute talk. I encourage everyone to ask your questions on the Slack channel and all the speakers to move to the platform after your talks to continue the discussions there. Kicking off the session we have **Daniela Calzetti** from UMass Amherst telling us about dust and star formation and galaxies, but apparently that's not the entire story. Take it away.

Thank you very much to the organizers for the kind invitation. This is a talk before all the exciting research we will hear in the next few talks. I decided to call it not the entire story because of the second slide. The second slide, the

rest of the story. For those, this is the conclusions. I will be talking of the dust on the stellar populations. I will not discuss the composition or other properties intrinsic to the dust, physical component. Also the observations of the universe. In particular one aspect that is the forefront during this talk is that the effects of dust, the star formation history of galaxies, with a degree, especially in the range which is the range of most of the upcoming surveys like the telescope and the U.K. telescope. They become a primary concern, especially if it would go on to obtain interesting formation about the properties of the object to specific galaxies. And also with the shapes, we have to rely on the red shift. It is usually mitigated by the high red shift galaxies with the dust, so the millimeter range which is a definition and therefore is at the handle of the amount of energy that has been taken away by dust in the process at this wavelength. The entire contribution is available, but then mitigated by the emission that the dust provides. However, it is not available for the telescope. And for this type of survey which we will have a large field, it is no match unfortunately. It has to be smaller, different observations, significant amounts over time. We needed to find ways to actually see the large service of galaxies. We will get the sample today in many talks, especially to try to limit the available range of the Genesee's using the argument. For those who don't work specifically on that, this is a plot from Conroy in 2013 showing the dust on the distribution of stellar population. So blue, energy density versus wavelength. You see the potential distribution of the stellar population and in the red UC the dust. It absorbs most of the photons, the obstacle, and then the energy that has been taken away from the optical is in the process in the IR. Even if the dust is a component of the galaxies red shift, it has a dramatic effect. We are also, most of us are familiar on a ways, the effects of dust on the cosmic star formation. So on the left-hand side you see two plots. They are from recent papers showing that the infrared, the red appoints, the right of bar with the density dominates over the UV observed. So the amount of star formation rate that is processed in the infrared is captured mostly by the dust emission rather than the dash sorry, rather than the UV. There are many, publishers have that, and it's a balanced view by collaborators on what are the unknowns? Ideally what we would like to end up as the plot on the right which was published in 2014. It would bring all this information here and try to understand how actually this star formation rate, has behaved in the red shift. Already looking at the left-hand side plot we see that the effects of dust on our measurements, just using the optical of the star formation rate is there depending on which objects are there. It is the effect on the stellar masses, but it is a significant amount of infrared. Neglecting that underestimates your densities and stellar masses by 20%. Why do we care about having the accurate star formation rate? This is a nice plot from collaborators in 2015 showing that decreasing the density to the universe can help constrain the model of galaxy evolution. Now the effect of dust is also more ancient than just the properties of galaxies. Our interpretation of cosmology, and particular to key goals is to conduct that using the lens and populations. Both the metals require regression, but for more than 90% of the galaxies that were surveyed by these facilities, there will not be spectroscopic, we have to rely on redshifts with accuracy, with great accuracy. We have a talk later this afternoon. Understanding the effects of that will become paramount before obtaining unbiased measurements of the dark energy and dark matter. Moving into the measuring sources in every ionization. We all are way that we will not be measuring which exactly because of the -- we need to extrapolate information on the redshifts. This dark becomes the concern and therefore understanding how and under what conditions the galaxies become leakers has to contain with the effects of changing into the effect. In terms of the leakage, I have the next two explain it more clearly. On the left-hand side you have a stellar distribution entity dust distribution by little stars. The dust distribution is in the right of screen. It is in one case, homogeneous mixture with the stars and the other case it is in front of all the stars. And although you have the same identical distributions of dust and stars individually, changing the relative distribution changes the output. On the right-hand side I'm showing that for the top configuration of dust and stars, the output is not very different from the input. You become extremely sensitive to the outermost layer of stars. The layer of stars closest. While in the second configuration, you can immediately see that it significantly there. In this case the input and output are described as a flux density, mutual densities as a function. So the next question you want to ask is, okay, given this, how do we measure and quantify the effect of dust? You might already have understood from the very first, the second slide that a relatively cheap way to obtain gross measurement of the effects of dust is to measure its impact and the UV range. Those that are easily obtainable with the standard dust techniques. It is relatively easy to measure. We can always measure the slope or the color. Of course if you have additional information, you can measure the match of the energy that was taken away from the UV optical in the infrared. And so you can have a slope of gross measurement of the dust by taking the total amount of energy in the IR over what you observed in the UV, or the infrared success. And that is marked by the slope. And so in one case the infrared UV, the match, it gives the match. They are independent, but possibly correlated measures of the impact of dust. And indeed the starburst, looking at these operations on the left-hand side plot you have the infrared success measured as the dash measured as the total and the slope. And early investigations found that there was actually correlation

between the two. Marked by a very clear sequence with the -- as what has been known. In particular the correlation is a continuation curve when some used for various applications. Now once you start moving away from the regime of concentrated monolithic starbursts, they start forming galaxies, that is where the star formation is no longer the single dominating lamp in the center of the galaxy. It's more like a popcorn type of situation which just come up and extinguish themselves. Of course the measurements and the results become more complicated. Indeed a few years after the first plot they were showing the correlation between the success and the caller, additional investigations came out plotting more galaxies. And a wider range of galaxies into this plot. Marking actually a range of behaviors as well. This behavior has been interpreted many different ways including for instance potential variations and continuations of the galaxy. And indeed the next plot shown the curve is far from being a unique trend and many of the systems and galaxies. I call it the continuation curve and I mentioned this earlier, an extension curve is when you have a layer of dust in front of a single star or one single point line, resource like the equator. Entity continuation curve actually is the, you have a lot of dust, extended screen or distribution of dust mixing and extended stellar population, therefore the, scattering and variable optical tests across the distribution. The variety of potential geometries mark themselves in a range of distinguishing curves. As I stated earlier, these Reformation history. What is the effect of the star formation history? If you remove the infrared formation and practically put the red screen in front of the long-wave like this plot, what you end up having or surveying is the red line up to the micron. In that case you would have a very hard time trying to understand whether it is the slope or the general red is the outlook of this distribution is due to the effects of dust or due to the effects of a stellar population. In addition to the complex geometry that star, dust can present to you you also have the problem that you have to deal with star formation histories. Indeed the potential there for the plot could be affected by the histories, being explored. In particular we have a collection of plots and I apologize, none of the plots I am showing gives the full justice to really these topics. I apologize for those, to provide a summary. On this plot, they suggest that the plot which is represented in various forms and different photos could be due to effects of the star formation history. Like changing in the curves, the effect of the star formation history is not only to change the slope of the population, but also to change the zero-point, so where the slope is one there is absolutely no dust. You can see it clearly in the top right plot and the bottom left plot where you see the zero points, very small values of infrared emission doesn't go over two minus two which is the slope for the star-forming stellar population. However, these explanations rely on the assumption that you are looking at the same objects across all values of the slope and while you can control that for simulations and therefore make that, it's hard to do for observational conditions. What you actually get, making assumptions is that you are seeing each step less red of a higher IR X object. Identifying which are the objects, which are the similar objects around this plot, tells you that by showing this curve you have proven a correlation that is not a proven causation. One way to prove it or address it in some form and shape is actually to zoom into the regions or galaxies and model them. This has been attempted, so by no means is that the first attempt, but one of the very few attempts with a much smaller. The reason it is important is because if you have a region, 100-200, you can reasonably assume that the region is dominated by a single population, starbursts, or approximate star formation population. If you have the region then you're going to model that, you're going to make assumptions about the history. In the plots I'm sure, by a group I am a collaborator of with a nearby Starbucks galaxy, these galaxies, it's not a whole galaxy starburst, but it's nuclear. It is actually a strong star formation, several units above the star formation if you consider the extended galaxy. If you divide this region in several regions and model each of them, first of all if you look at the entire galaxy and the starburst center of this galaxy, it is full of the data relation of starburst. 5 minutes. Thank you. These are both regions that is a bit qualified as a starburst, especially that of course by definition, but they're falling off. Suggesting that something is happening. Now Lee something is not likely by the star formation. It is normally occurring in star formations like the situation of the galaxy. Indeed when you model the individual regions of star formation in the center of this galaxy you immediately see what it represents in the plot and the bottom left of my slide, the star formation rate is far from being increasing, but there is a short of a U shape meaning the galaxy, the center was forming at a rather significant pace, between about 15 and 300 million years ago and then started to become that spirit possibly due to the fact that the star formation is there with a bar. If you take a look at the star formation history of the star into account you can construct come up from intrinsic slope, what would be the effect of the region on the plot marked by NGC3351. Now the gray area is not in a curve. You actually can smoothly take the same distribution of regions, stellar populations and simply become a proportionally increased the dust in front of it and the ways that it sees a currently known distributed. Meaning they have to be increasing lock steps. Cannot be increased in different ways. This is what a curve for means. Please do not take these. Okay. It is simply here to show that if you assume an intrinsic distribution implied by the star formation history and project it to the amount of dust contained in the center, you were called exactly the IR X better. So my conclusions is that quantifying the effects of dust are key for

quantifying the evolution of galaxies and constraining the geometry of the dark universe. And even the most dust formation will not be available for a large survey. We have to establish cheaper methods for which the emission lines. And these are cheap methods, important. The cheap method which was use a slope to recover the emission, so the entire energy by the infrared, but of course that doesn't seem to work as well for a less active galaxy. Various orders have suggested this implies other variations of the curve or the star formation history or a combination all three. One indicator, the star formation history is the predominant effect in the offset from the relation. Not so much variations in the curve as the intrinsic distribution of the stellar population. These also implies that often in the star formation histories which are often there, a critical revisit to accommodate a much wider range of potential star formation histories and galaxies. This will be crucial for determining the situation, their effects on galaxies end of the effect on the physical quantities you are trying to determine. Thank you very much.

Thank you for the enlightening talk. We just got a question. Christopher was asking if supernova feedback and explain the U-shaped curve of star formation rates versus $H\alpha$? That's an excellent question. The U-shaped possibly, it could be an activity variation in the feeding of the star formation. This is a galaxy that has a well-documented influx of gas that is feeding the central bar and the star formation. A potential variation in the process might actually affect the way the center is bursting or not Burstein. Of course the feedback from the supernova may actually have the shut off formation at least close to the end of the time.

Okay. Thanks. We have a second question. Should we really still be using the IR X data given that the sophistication of modern codes? The modern codes actually are the assumptions on the curve that they're using. And those are embedded in times with the codes. So starting the IR racks, it gives us some handlin on what variations should adopt and how physical and visible they are. But that's another excellent question. Thank you. I want to ask, could other factors such as density because that and how could they best be distinguished? You are asking about the curve? Yes, they can change. In my experience every time you are dealing with a galaxy, so an extended region rather than a point source, the two dominant affects our lead geometry star formation history. In the shape of the curve which is determined by distribution and properties of dust planes is actually second, second parameter typically. Thank you. That would conclude our talk session. Thank you so much.

Next up we have **Andrew Battisti** from ANU and he will tell us about how to sweep away the dust. I would like to thank the organizers for giving this talk today. My name is Andrew Battisti. I'm at the Australian National University. Today I will talk about work I been doing, trying to understand the evolution of dust regulation curbs and the function of red shift. She gave an excellent overview so I don't have to spend much time on the motivation, but to remind everyone. Dust attenuation can significantly alter the galaxies and as she mentioned, there is large variation among galaxies for the wavelength dependent wave. It's known as the attenuation curve. And this of course impacts the ability to accurately derive things like redshifts and properties. In particular, the photos are something that's important for a lot of the dark energy science that is planned for the facilities like Roman. And so typically one can account for this dust attenuation if you have made/far infrared observations, but as she mentioned these will be unavailable for the vast majority of galaxies that are surveyed with Roman, simply because of the survey areas that those facilities will be looking at. Of course this poses a major challenge for the precision cosmology. And galaxy evolution studies these. To understand this, I'm using the program that uses both the G1 oh two and a 141 grism, the imaging for about 480 fields, half a square degree come about three times the area of that, but that was only about G141, so the majority of the fields contain both of them. The data is all reduced and publicly available at the URL that is shown on the top of the slide. Various catalogs are currently being produced by the team, and particular I want to highlight the emission catalog that is prepared by McCalla. It contains 800 Mission line galaxies. For my study I am interested in for which we could use the data emission line simultaneously. This allows us to, gives us a range of .75-1.5. Where is he only had G141 you would have to use a much smaller. Roughly half of the galaxies in the catalog or red shift in this window and so there is a very large sample that we can use for studying. Of course the downside, this is a parallel, the majority of the field are randomly located in the sky with respect to where we typically do like deep fields like in the cases of the legacy fields. And of course this means they don't have deep data. And so recently there's been a lot of effort from the team with photometric data outside of just like HST imaging. So with data, it contains up to four bands combining that. We have also obtained for about half the fields, the imaging which this focuses mainly on the deepest fields and other members of the team have led programs to obtain the imaging and optical

wavelengths which progress, UV and optical wavelengths. I highlight two programs in the bottom. Those are the ones that I lied to myself, mainly focusing on getting imaging which probes the ultraviolet or galaxies around redshifts of one. And the panel on the bottom right illustrates basic ideas behind the analysis for this project which is to compare the bread that it has for a particular galaxy relative to the measured over the depth. It is the ratio relative to what is expected for the intrinsic ratio and the recombination. As referring to the original starburst paper from Daniela where she use this method to derive the curve. The fact that you have these two parameters with depth and knowledge, you can empirically derived the curve. So of course we have, we are dealing with a lot of different types of data and different quality and depth, so a lot of work is put forth into trying to develop a pipeline for the data. In particular the optical and Spitzer data, we are utilizing the software to obtain consistent data sets. The panels on the bottom sort of demonstrate how this works and practice. The left image is HST, the middle is a Magellan G band image for the field. And combined knowledge of the sources with HST, combining both facilities and then extract the sources. And the image on the right is the residual map after the source extraction. It indicates that sources are being properly extracted. And so the catalogs for the Spitzer imaging, hopefully they will be available next year. Please stay tuned for that because it will enable a lot of new science can be done with the rich data sets. And so here I just want to demonstrate a couple of examples where we have really good data for both emission lines. It is undetected. So we will have to utilize that to characterize the depths, but these two cases are, these are two cases in which the data is detected. I use the demonstration, what the typical galaxies look like. So for the galaxies, I'm using a custom version of the spectrum modeling code, but it incorporates attenuation curve in the future, now this is important because you want to try to mitigate the effects that the assumption for the attenuation curve has only derived physical properties. In particular, mass is an important thing for the study because I have to use it to correct for the fact that it is blended with the grism data. I'm using by this 2018 which depends on stellar mass and red shift. The panel on the left shows the grism data and the distribution for a source that has a very low, optical depth. It consists of zero. You can see that SED is very blue and indicates it has very little reddening. If you look at the source on the right it has a much larger value. Accordingly you see the SED galaxy is much redder. This is what you expect if the correlated to each other. there still a lot of work that needs to be done for some of the fainter galaxies in terms of obtaining their continuum spectra, but for robust subsample of galaxies where you have multiple lines, I can already form some kind of analysis to see how things seem to work so far. That is what I'm showing here. I also want to mention that we are excluding galaxies for which have significant contributions. Your slides are no longer showing. Ohno. Can you verify? Let me try re-sharing. Sorry about that. Okay. Now we can see it. Thank you. Was it on this slide? The end of last one. Sorry. Just to quickly reiterate, we are using a subsample of galaxies currently because we don't have the full data set available for continuum stacking. It shows the mass distribution of the current example. And the current separating the UV slope. And so there are roughly hundred sources in each been and I will just color coat these samples. Going from the blue West SED to the redder, these are corresponding to the panels here. These are the spectra that are normalized. And so what you can see very clearly is that the bluer line, the emission line become noticeably redder or weaker as you go to the redder SED's. And so the panel on the left is showing the median SED's for the four bands of UB slopes. Of course they're getting redder as they increase the UV slope. They also course finally larger value. The top right panel shows the relationship between the UV slope, it's a way of characterizing the behavioral. You can see for these cases the galaxies seem to behave more similarly to red shift zero galaxies. 2 minutes. Sorry? 2 minutes. Thank you very much. Of course the plan is to sample in more ways and perhaps this will change as a function of different types of properties. There will be a talk later in the session that will talk about the relationship for other samples that she is using. The bottom right panel illustrates the effective average attenuation curve using the SED's on the left. And you can see and live somewhere between the red shift of zero relationship and the red shift zero using the sample. This might not be unexpected since you might have the case of evolution end of the going from 0 to 2. Apparently it is not what's calling that evolution. The future work is to try to utilize the entire WISP sample, building up sample sizes of hopefully a few thousand galaxies in order to ban the samples in different ways such as stellar mass, the rate, Metallicity, things like that. Do characterize if there is an evolution. And with that hopefully bridge our understanding of how the continuation curve varies to low red shift to high red shift. Just in my last line here I wanted to highlight the future with Roman Euclid, and particular understanding that. Both Roman and Euclid will feature spectroscopy. It will provide the ability to measure from 1-2. So the game changing aspect of these facilities as we've heard is the field of improvement. WISP which covered have a square degree can be covered. The baseline prism highlighted to the survey is supposed to be something that's with 2,000 square degrees. You can imagine there's going to be dramatic increase in our numbers of the emission galaxies we can use to study. It will be revolutionary for our ability to characterize the understanding, our understanding of dust evolving, going from 0 to 2. I

think it's going to be very important for application to go higher. I'm very excited for the science that can be done at these facilities. I will stop and be happy to take any questions. Thank you.

Thanks, Andrew. I had a question. With the increase and sample size as expected from the field of view given by Roman, much better as you expect the characterization to be in terms of your constraining the bars and whatnot. That's a great question. As Daniela mentioned in her talk, I glossed over this, but the major issue with trying to characterize curves empirically in the way that I'm doing as, you know, you're comparing different galaxies like more galaxies to last and there can be issues with the fact that we want sample you are using compared to another isn't 1-1. And if you have more galaxies than you can pin things into being more similar in terms of different kinds of properties. You can collect a whole bunch of galaxies and different amounts. That might provide less uncertainty in how you characterize the attenuation. Does that answer your question? Yes.

I want to squeeze in one more question. Great talk for galaxies, what fraction of your sample has on physical ratios attributed to zero dust that has been seen in other surveys? That's a great question. I haven't looked into this with too much detail yet, but it's a large fraction. It's probably like half of them. I think most of that has to do with how the continuum is being fit for the grism data. In particular for the grism, it's typically really noisy. And so you can identify peaks which perhaps, at least from like what I stack them, the values are more physically than what you expect in terms of being both zero. Thank you. That's it for a time. Thank you Andrew.

Next up we have **Claude-Andre Faucher-Giguere** from Northwestern telling us about the NRC virialization. Thank you very much. The implications and evolutions of the star formation. The key concept here will be ICV, I will explain the emphasis of it. We will also look at the poster, the lead for most of the results. And I'm sure Jonathan will be happy to be answering questions too. One of the questions for this work is when do galaxies have large disks and why? For example, what is observed to be most common with the luminosity function, while dwarf galaxies are often irregular and more massive galaxies often have mergers. The answer to this question isn't explained by classic theories, momentum and halos because the momentum is nearly independent of mass. Observations are also shown, increasingly here when we go to evolution, the red shift is another aspect that we would like to explain. And Roman will be very important for this problem of formation because the resolution is needed to form morphologies of galaxies, especially at red shift and Roman will pull the morphologies with 100 times greater field. The results that I will show today are based on FIRE simulations. These are cosmological as humans that were resolved by the stellar medium to show galaxies in these contexts. As well as to model individual star-forming. Here we see a video of the formation from this project. The top is color-coded by gas temperature. Cool gas is in green and at the bottom we see the stars as formed by the simulation. In the simulations we model feedback from the processes, supernova, stellar winds as well as radiation. The feedback sometime is dependent, so the feedback is tied to the popular stellar population model. In this sense the feedback incident in the simulation, but they have the property such as the structure, medium, star formation with feedback. Galaxies scale outflow, really depictions of the simulation. One thing to note from this video is that the morphology, is highly clumpy and highly dynamic, but you can see here in the gas correspond to the analog of observed galaxy. All in this case the red shift, that's a large out of which a nice stellar disk eventually forms. And we have a galaxy. So we have dozens of simulations like this one from the FIRE project. Here is a visual sense of a simulation sample. These are mock HD of a FIRE zoom in simulation. You can see the level of detail that is involved in calculations like this one it is also showing how they form by a shift of zero with the halo, so the simulations are in fact a useful tool to study this formation. Now turning to the video from two slides ago, the formation of a large, long leads to disks and late times is actually a phenomenon in the FIRE simulation. It was not specific to that one simulation. And generally speaking that occurs when galaxies reach a star. Now in addition to this transition and morphology, the simulated galaxies FIRE, at the same time experience a very clear transition into the connector of the star formation history, transitioning from highly valuable at high red shift to much more low red shift as indicated in this plot of normalized reformation rates. Finally we also find that in the simulations, very powerful and visible at high shift actually, eventually goes to one galaxy for each stellar mass, two times ten to the tenth stroller mass. We would like to understand what drives these transitions. This is phenomenology that we have seen for several years now in FIRE simulation, but it's only now that we have a very promising series of different transitions together as well as the inner circle galaxy. So first, some general background on CGM physics. The CGM can be in the front regime. The first is one the cooling time of the gas is everywhere shorter and then the halo. At that point it

goes to halos, the galaxy doesn't see falling gas coming from a color point of view. The regime, the cooling time in which the other halo becomes long enough for the CGM to stay hot. But the gas still cools rapidly. It is similar, the central galaxy. Finally there is a third regime, along everywhere in the halo. Such as the entire CGM is hot, all the way to the central galaxy. This is when in our terminology we say the inner CGM has finally realized, and our main result is that this is an important transition for the central galaxy. This transition occurs in approximately when the ratio of the cooling time, the inner halo becomes the unity which occurs rapidly and halos of mass stents as well as solar mass. Next, here is an example of the outside, so they gas temperature in the halo, the bottom is punctuation at the same red shift going from one to the left to zero on the right. If we focus first at the red shift of one, we see the NRC GM has a lot to blue. And many low-pressure channel, that's around the central galaxy. This is significant because the low-pressure channel, channels and to the supernova feedback from star formation can effectively below. As a result of that there isn't a nice middle because it keeps being destroyed. Go forward and to the simulation, the entire halo there is now a very nice disk, this long-lived disk is made possible by the much more uniformed confinement of the central galaxy by hard to guess which a near uniform halo. Next what I want to do is show you evidence in the transition in the halo. Different transitions and galaxy properties that we saw before. 2 minutes. The measure flows for two different examples simulations, color-coded by the issue of the cooling at .10 which is the measure of what the CGM virialization. And in this unit, it occurs when the ratio crushes the threshold of one. What can you see is that it corresponds to the establishment of nearly circular orbit for the gas. This transition from blue to red, the morphology is higher red shift. Next here is how it relates to star formation the simulation. The top panel here, low rate at one-tenth of the radius. The bottom panel is a timescale ratio that tells us. And the time of ICV is indicated by the curve or line which goes through the entire column. And what you can see is that a fluctuation in the star formation rate in the panel as well as the mass, it suggests that. This is in fact genetic of different simulation and our sample as I have shown. So both star formation rates as well as mass corresponds to positive values in these panels. Here is a cartoon picture to explain what we think is going on. At high red shift and low mass halo the gas burners freely and feedback occurs effectively in the low-pressure halo. This results and star formation cycle in which they galaxy repeatedly blows itself apart. That is why we can't form. When galaxies reach a hello mass with solar mass, it can find potential galaxy and also suggests, galactic wins. From that point on, the long-lived galaxy disk allows the feedback to the star formation rate to its value. Know that in detail, on halo mass, but the central galaxy and circular velocity, and Metallicity of the inner CGM. There are more predictions that can be used to test the theory. Let me conclude here. In summary, the fire simulation formation of large galaxies, the transition to study star formation rates as well as the galaxy wins and a low rent shift galaxies all occur at the same time and we argue that this happens when the inner CGM completes virialization. This is an interesting connection between CGM and galaxy evolution. This would be useful to test thanks to its ability to resolve galaxy morphology and a large sample, especially at higher shift. Thank you. I will be happy to take questions. Thank you.

I want to remind all the speakers that you should always engage everyone else on the slack channel afterwards. I guess I will squeeze in one quick question. Do you have, and all of your models, do you always have the CGM at the same stellar mass? It is approximately the case, yeah, and a simulation, in a CGM, approximately at the hello mass, two times ten, approximately stellar mass because of the consistency of the halo mass relationship. I will try to emphasize on the slide here, if you look in detail, there are some variance on simulation to simulation. You take that a variance in the stellar mass or halo mass can be, to a large extent explained by the theory onto the side of the central galaxy, and circular velocity, and to be Metallicity of the NRC GM. He went to think about this, it governs the cooling time ratio here. They're actually writing a paper in which he compares on the galaxy by galaxy basis for which we have observational measurements at the galaxy side and galaxy Metallicity. Whether we expect this to perform or not. I encourage you to ask you more about that. Great. Thanks. There are more questions for you. If you can move over and answer them that would be Great.

Next up we have **Hermine Landt**. Unfortunately she told me this morning that due to local lockdown restrictions and the COVID-19 situation she has now done a prerecorded talk. If you have questions, please post them to slack and she will try to answer them in a timely session. The moderator is not going to play her slide. This is Russell. You see my screen? I do. I will enter full screen mode and play it. Thank you. Hi, I am Hermine Landt. Today I would like to tell you the results that we have gained and hopefully in the future we will want to extend it to space. This is the Astro chemistry of the dust around the supermassive black holes and the new era of transient infrared sky value. The inner

structure is complex, but it cannot be spatially resolved with optical and infrared frequency. It would not be possible to do so and in the foreseeable future. The scales, to give you an idea are well below and in the near resources they are well below -- we have optical infrared information, emission from the accretion region, and makes the infrared for the telescope. Time domain astronomy can probe unresolved sizes, especially through the optical and infrared because there, it's the primary variation and the other one reacts to it. In the optical we have the dust and we radiate to the infrared. And the emission lines can be observed in the optical and infrared. If we can that accumulate sites of this, we can measure. This can be done with the coordinated aim of a long year, currently extensive but with very little time. However the information is very limited. Never the less, interesting results have been obtained for about 28, not that money and we know now that the radius is about 10-a hundred. Quite small. This is what becomes to be smaller as measured in the infrared. Furthermore we have seen from these studies that the radius relationship that starts out to be very important. You can determine the radius. The luminosity follows a similar slope as we have previously observed already. This actually tells you that it's performing. Now we have taken the infrared monitoring a step further because it has become available that can be used to serve the time. And it is very powerful, we can measure temperature. Now this very limited study, it can measure two things at the same time. The radius using the thermal equilibrium relationships with the temperature and then the response time itself just by entering one to the other. If you compare the two you can actually, as it goes into the thermal, you can determine the time, if you can measure them both simultaneously. The information on temperature alone is also very important because its value is close approximation and the variation you can measure, temperature tells you how close it is. In AGN, and the stars for example, it's very interesting to study this. Temperature measurement, this is given by the infrared spectrum. The genomes -- so the rise of sources, when finished -- 48 and 2017 and 519 just recently last year. Resources are still ongoing, they have a very interesting radius measured. I would like now to talk briefly about the results for NGC, we have measured the time, and if we calculate now with the equation I presented earlier, I assume the large range and modified -- small sizes you can see from the values that these are very different. 16, 400, and even 600. This is all due to that. The measured response time, this tells you it is fewer. This can be carbon, larger expected. In smaller -- and now we go here and we measure about 1600K, we know there around the temperature. And carbon can supplement on 1800-2000K. Now this is the first, it should have already gone. If this was dominated rather than the infrared, then we should not observe the variation, but we do. It's an indication it is heating and cooling. Which means most are dominated by the carbon and temperature. Now with spectroscopy you can do the variable spectrum. You can study the variation and spectrum shape. I will show it here for the results. The very start of their kind, so we are learning from. In 5548 we can see as we recover the accretion spectrum and then larger than 1 micron. We see the dust. The variable and the spectrum means it is showing black, both a similar S, meaning it is one that dominates the emission. It seems that we are picking up only one component in the variability. It means there are at least two components. At the moment, we note the two components are, most likely the spectrum component, it is still to. In any case, one of the components, accretion disk, spectrum is revealed at the wavelength, very important information because the other radius, we don't know how big it can be. And especially we don't know if it can be larger than the gravity radius. Breaking apart. So now an excellent opportunity for us with several missions, plans and the advantage is going to the weather. We cannot depend on it anymore. The data is guaranteed, processed, and time. And very crucial we have the absolute flux calibration and there because we have to see. However, some of the disadvantages...

Did the video, audio drop-off? We are working on it. Okay. Thank you. May be an interest of time, if the prerecorded talk can be made available to everyone. It looks like Russell is trying to restart it, but there was only 2 minutes remaining. It will be available on slack to watch the complete talk and remainder of the talk. Great. Thank you so much. Yeah. I wanted to thank Hermine Landt for recording this great talk and thank you Russell for playing it for us. If you can leave questions for her on the slack channel and the last couple minutes of her talk that would be Great.

If we can then move on to the final speaker and this session, **Anahita Alavi**. She'll be telling us about the measurements for high redshift dwarf galaxies. The floor is yours. Thank you, Vivienne. Okay. Thank you very much for this amazing meeting and for the organizers for giving me this opportunity to talk about my research that I have been involved with. Today I'm going to talk about the dust at the nation measurement for high redshift dwarf galaxies. I know that hearing all this amazing talks, you are now convinced that why the dust is important to measure, but just, for all the amazing talks that we hear, many galaxy observers that measure for galaxies for local galaxies -- this is because that all the lights that we see come all the lights that are amended and the galaxies have to hide through the

dust, to reach us. I think this slide is coming, this UV light where we measure the light 4.7 star formation rate. Or when we use that to measure them. Or to measure a stellar mass or if we are losing the emission lines and then we will take the line ratio -- or we use the line. For all these properties we need to understand the dust. While we care about dust in the dwarf galaxies in the specific talk, here I would like to show a very simple example. This is a plot on the left, a plot done in 2014, it is showing the star formation history. Using the UV lights of galaxies with the images. The way that people make this plot is to a different red shift, they take the luminosity function as shown here on the right and then they just take the luminosity function down to different luminosity -- down to different luminosity magnitudes. And then from this they estimate the density. And then they just add some factor or some convention to go from the luminosity to the density. For this commission they need to assume the connection. The way that they've been doing this so far, as been mentioned is that they have some estimate for the more massive galaxies. And they usually assume the definition is zero and that is how we connect and we drive the plots. What if this assumption is not correct? We need to go directly and see how much dust exists, however, so far we are using the relation for the galaxy to the lower mass. We just assume a zero dust. In order to have the dust in the low mass galaxy we used two examples. The first example is the lens galaxies. The example of the lens galaxies and also in other clusters, another massive cluster called Abell. For these galaxies, it's actually about 100 lensed galaxies, up to 20 high magnification. We actually have been obtaining a more fine to actually assist -- and from this survey we have a sample of about 36 galaxies where we have a good cover, but for some of them we have very good -- also for this, the correction is a small, and also -- and also the galaxies here are 1.6. In order to compare the sample of lens galaxies that we have here, some of the other samples that people have been, people have been basically studying, for example most of the survey right here, they study the normal forming galaxies at about one. As you see this is -- this plot is showing the mass distribution. As we see in the sample, a factor -- an order of two lower mass, so this survey is a low mass galaxy. The second sample is from this survey, as you hear, very nice introduction by Andrew. This is a survey, this is a survey getting free emission lines and galaxies in order to build a sample. Some criteria in order to make sure that we have the prediction, alpha, beta, low contamination and the measurement. The galaxies -- this is a slide where we are comparing these examples. The red sample on top and the WISP sample on the bottom. We are showing the distribution. As you can see, the distribution of lensed galaxies, so by combining these we are covering a wide range of stellar mass. Looking at very abundant, but very low mass dwarf galaxies. And that is looking at sort of, ten to the nine, at work galaxies. And also I'm showing this slide with the stellar masses for the example. For the first result, I would like to share this plot where we are basically comparing the Y axis and finding the optical depth on the X axis. The Y axis is sort of the stellar attenuation. The X axis is the solution. It showing the value from 2.86 which is the value where there is no dust from the combination. Here in this plot I should mention that -- it has the lensed a sample. We see the individual galaxies and there is a scatter and it is a scatter showing that there are other factors and other parameters that are playing roles here, but if you just look at what is the value or the stacked value as shown by the red diamond we can see that the dwarf galaxies simply following either this line or the Green line. These lines are showing actually different, the purple lines are the cause, the green alliance, but the dashed line that means if assume there are more nebular region has suggested by this paper. This really assumes the same attenuation or any nebular region. It seems like you'd work galaxies can be explained with the line, the curve assuming similar attenuation in the nebular region. Or they can be also -- assuming more attenuation. In the next plot here we are showing this correlation between the nebular attenuation or the X axis and the Y-axis. 2 minutes. Sorry? Okay. That is from the sample. Here I am adding the stack from this and the stack from me nebular from the lensed sample. As you see here, most of the galaxies and lensed galaxies are following the current we had seen before. That as you go to a lower mass, the nebular attenuation. The next plot is very similar, but only Y axis we have the stellar attenuation. Again, the pink is good, more massive galaxies from the sample and the red diamond and the blue bar from the lensed sample respectively. So here at nine it seems our measurement is with what we have seen before. As we go to a lower stellar mass, it seems that this relation, this sort of stipulation that we had for the more massive galaxies, this means that if we just extrapolate from the more massive galaxies we would get basically zero dots, but this observation is telling us that there is dust in the galaxy that we have to call for. I think it's an important point in this plot. Now why do we need the Roman telescope? As we saw, we have this, suffering from these statistics to a high level of contamination. But the Roman telescope can actually help us to solve this problem. Because of the very large, more than 100, it provides a lot of galaxies with data and because it provides, it has the ability to basically take the angle, we can solve for the contamination. And here I'm showing the example of accumulation that I am doing now as a collaboration for another project. It's a great high latitude for the survey where we are basically simulating what we will see with the Roman telescope. The point here is to show that -- for the same galaxies I'm showing the yellow circle which you can see on the right for the low line we cannot see the spectra. So then we can

solve for the contamination. And of course Roman because it provides a very large view. It can actually observe this type of environment. We can actually study it in this environment. As is suggested by some simulation that the galaxies environment can have different -- here I just will leave the summary. I will take questions. Thank you.

Thank you. I was wondering. If you could elaborate more on the gather that was found by you -- by the dwarf sample and whether or not when you have increased sample size from a rural man, whether you expect that to populate that same span of more or if it's going to do, who knows what? You mean this one? Yes. Or at least speculate on the scatter a little bit. Do you mean this plot? Any of them. Thank you for this question. This is a good question. The scatter that you see in this or other plots as well, it is showing that there are other playing roles here. For example with the low mass galaxies, the star formation history. The galaxies, the low mass galaxies are, head of the star formation history and that star formation history can easily change and they are scattered because of that. It might be it simply different with the star formation history. When we have a larger sample and of course with what we have with Roman, so we don't just rely, we can use the individual galaxy and then basically, it may be you look at the difference, the different property. For example, the star formation rate. Let's say this individual data with a star formation rate, to see if the star formation rates are sitting in different parts. Larger numbers, it can help us to study those other that are claiming a role here. We cannot do much here. Did I answer your question? Perfect. That's fine. There are more questions for you on the slack channel. If you can go ahead and address those. That would be great. At this time I will cut to the session. I want to thank all the speakers today. I will pass the virtual microphone back to the moderator. Thank you.

Thank you to all of our speakers, and thank you Vivian for chairing this session. During the poster break here we are going to be looping poster abstracts, but we encourage you to go to the slack channel where you can also ask questions to the poster presenters. We apologize that the audio dropped off in the final 90 seconds of Hermine Landt's talk, but we did post the full talk in the appropriate channel. You can view the final 90 seconds as well as the whole talk and continue to ask questions there. We will take a break. We will be back at 12:30 p.m. for session eight.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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